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Research Article

Parental Social Support and Students Academic Achievement: A Study of Gilgit Baltistan Secondary Schools

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Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 18-Oct-23 Revised: 02-Dec-23 Accepted: 18-Dec-23 Published: 31-Dec-23	The study was conducted to check the role of parental social support in students academic achievement at secondary level in Gilgit Baltistan. The study was descriptive in nature and survey method was used to collect the data. The population consisted of all the secondary level students of Tehsil Roundu, district Skurdu. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw the sample from the population, and the researcher selected (320) students as a sample. A questionnaire based on Five Point Likert Scale was developed for students. The researcher personally collected the data. Statistical Software for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to examine the data with the help of frequency and percentage. It was found that most of the respondents were agreed that the parents help whenever need and they help in emotional development and support me in everything. Moreover, respondents stayed agreed that the parents are the source of comfort for children they can count on parents when thing go wrong.
Keywords:	Parental Social Support, Academic Achievement, Secondary Schools
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Introduction

Social support is the awareness and actuality that one is cared for, has support accessible from other people, and most popularly, that one is part of a supportive social network. These supportive resources can be emotional (e.g., nurturance), informational (e.g., advice), or companionship (e.g., sense of belonging); tangible (e.g., financial assistance) or intangible (e.g., personal advice). Social support can be measured as the observation that one has assistance available, the actual received help, or the degree to which a person is integrated into a social network (Gorostiaga & Huedo Medina, 2021).

Social support has remained linked to many profits for both physical and mental health, but "social support" (chatting about friends) is not always beneficial. Social support is often known as a main section of solid relationships and strong mental health. Essentially, social support involves having a network of family and friends that you can turn to in times of requirement (Noret, Hunter & Rasmussen, 2020).

According to Armstrong (2018) social support refers to how individuals perceive friends, family members and others as bases available to deliver material, psychological and overall support during times of need. Apparent social support has been dependably related to well-being, as the perceived levels of support, love, and care can provide positive experiences (Zhong, Wang & Nicholas, 2020).

Parental social support refers to the emotional, involved, and informational assistance that parents provide to their children. This support can manifest in various ways, such as providing encouragement, offering help with homework, attending parent-teacher conferences, and creating a supportive home environment for learning (Honkaniemi & Quesnel-Vallee, 2016).

Parental social support is a critical factor in children's academic achievement. When parents provide emotional, instrumental, and informational support, children are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and successful in their academic pursuits. However, it is essential to recognize that academic achievement is unfair by multiple factors, and a holistic approach that considers various aspects of a child's life is necessary to promote educational success. Establishing Boundaries, setting clear and consistent boundaries is important for social support (Garipey, Honkaniemi & Quesnel-Vallee, 2016).

Academic achievement is a multifaceted concept that encompasses a student's performance, skills, and accomplishments within an educational setting. It goes beyond grades and involves various aspects such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and effective communication (Bakrie & Syaifuddin, 2023).

One crucial component of academic achievement is maintaining high grades. Consistently excelling in coursework reflects a student's understanding of the material and their ability to apply concepts. However, true academic achievement extends beyond the realm of examinations. It involves active engagement in class, asking questions, and participating in discussions, demonstrating a depth of comprehension beyond rote memorization (Singh, Sharma & Singh, 2023).

The relationship between parental social support and children's academic achievement is a complex and multifaceted one. While parental social backing can have a helpful impact on children's academic performance, it is important to recognize that academic achievement is influenced by various factors, and parental support is just one piece of the puzzle (Rodríguez, Tinajero & Páramo, 2017).

Review of Related Literature

Social support

It can come from family, friends, neighbors, co-workers, and other public members. Social support can be a powerful barrier against stress and can help people cope with difficult life events (Stansfeld & Wilkinson, 2006). Social support refers to the psychological and material resources providing by a social network to help individuals cope with stress. Such social support may come in different forms and power involve. Helping a person with many daily tasks when they are ill or offering economic help when they are in need (Amorim-Ribeiro & Carneiro, 2022).

Social support refers to the assistance, care, and resources providing by individuals, communities, and organizations to help individuals cope with various challenges and enhance their well-being (Pasinringi & Sandy, 2022). It involves the presence of a network of family, friends, colleagues, and community members who offer emotional, contributory, or informational support during times of need or stress.

There are many different types of social support. Emotional support includes things like listening to someone when they are going through a tough time, providing comfort and encouragement, and offering words of encouragement (Olinder, DeAbreu, Greene, Haugstvedt, Lange, Majaliwa & Mahmud, 2022). Instrumental support includes things like providing financial assistance, helping with childcare, or running errands. Informational support includes things like providing advice, guidance, or information.

Types of social support

Social support can take various methods and can be classified into different types based on the source and nature of support. Here are some common types of social support.

Emotional Support

This type of support includes providing identification, understanding, and care to someone in need. It includes listening, offering comfort, and expressing concern to help individuals cope with emotional distress or difficult life situations (Chawla, 2020).

Instrumental Support

Instrumental support refers to providing tangible or practical assistance to someone. It can include helping with tasks, providing resources, or offering direct solutions to problems. Examples include financial assistance, helping with household chores, or offering transportation (Cacciatore & Thieleman, 2021).

Informational Support

Informational support involves providing guidance, guidance, and information to help individuals make informed decisions or understand a particular situation. It includes sharing knowledge, resources, or expertise to address specific needs or concerns.

Appraisal Support

Appraisal support focuses on providing feedback, evaluation, or constructive criticism to help individuals assess their abilities, skills, or performance. It can include giving encouragement, constructive feedback, or perspective to aid in problem-solving or decision-making processes (Adarkwah, 2021).

Companionship Support

Companionship support refers to providing social interaction, companionship, and a sense of belonging to combat feelings of loneliness or isolation. It involves spending time together, engaging in social activities, or simply being present for someone (Thangavel & Hedström, 2022).

Esteem Support

Esteem support involves providing recognition, praise, and encouragement to boost someone's self-esteem, self-worth, or confidence. It includes affirming and validating someone's abilities, achievements, or positive qualities.

Belonging Support

Belonging support focuses on creating a sense of community and inclusiveness. It involves promoting a supportive environment, fostering connections, and building social networks to help individuals feel accepted, valued, and part of a larger group (Sayfulloevna, 2023).

It's important to note that these types of social support are interconnected and can overlap in various situations. The type of support needed may vary depending on the individual's circumstances, preferences, and the specific challenges they are facing (Freak-Poli & Byles, 2022).

Parental social support is a comprehensive term that encompasses a variation of ways that parents can provide emotional, practical, and informational assistance to their children. It can be provided in a variety of ways, including through direct communication, modelling, and creating a supportive environment (Gottlieb & Bergen, 2010).

Parental social support

As an important source of social support for youngsters, parental social support refers to the accessibility of resources parents can provide their children to help them cope with problem (Olukoya & Aggleton 2005).

Parental social support refers to the help, resources, and emotional backing that parents receive from their social networks, including family members, groups, neighbors, and community organizations. It encompasses the various forms of support that parents may receive to help them meet the challenges and responsibilities of raising children (Weinraub & Wolf, 1983).

Parental social support refers to the support, understanding, and resources that parents receive from their social networks. With family, friends, and communities. It plays a crucial role in promoting the well-being of both parents and children. Parental social support can encompass various aspects, such as emotional support, practical help, and informational guidance (Yan & Deng, 2022).

Emotional support involves the provision of empathy, understanding, and encouragement to parents during challenging times. It can include listening to their concerns, offering a shoulder to lean on, and providing reassurance. Emotional support helps parents feel understood, validated, and less isolated, which can improve their mental and emotional happiness (Loveys & Sagar, 2022).

Practical help involves tangible assistance provided by social networks, such as family and friends. It can include assistance with childcare, household chores, transportation, or running errands (Thompson, 2022). Practical support can improve some of the burdens and responsibilities parents face, allowing them to have more time and energy to devote to their children.

Informational guidance refers to the sharing of knowledge, advice, and resources relevant to parenting. This can include information about child development, parenting strategies, accessing community services, and connecting with relevant support networks. Informational support empowers parents with knowledge and tools to make knowledgeable decisions and navigate the challenges of parenting effectively (Zhou & wang, 2022).

The presence of strong parental social support has been connected to numerous benefits for both parents and children. For parents, it can reduce stress levels, increase confidence, and promote overall well-being. It can also enhance parenting skills and reduce the risk of parental burnout. For children, parental social support contributes to their healthy development, emotional security, and positive relationships (Goldenberg, Brytek-Matera, 2022).

Communities and support networks play a vital role in development parental social support. They can provide spaces for parents to connect, share experiences, and seek guidance. Parenting classes, support groups, community centers, and online forums are examples of resources that facilitate parental social support (Townley, 2022).

Academic achievement

Academic achievement describes academic results that indicate the extent to which a student has achieved their learning goals. Academic achievement may refer to completing educational levels such as a bachelor's degree. Academic achievement is often measured through examinations or continuous assessments. Academic achievement is the extent to which a student or institution has achieved either short- or long-term educational goals. Achievement may be measured through students' grade point average, whereas for institutes, achievement may be measured through graduation rates (Garipey, Honkaniemi & Quesnel-Vallee, 2016).

Academic achievement typically refers to the successful completion of educational goals and the attainment of desired learning outcomes. It is often measured through grades, test scores, and other indicators of academic performance. Achievements in academia can occur at various levels, from primary and secondary education to higher education and beyond. Here are some key factors and considerations related to academic achievement: Academic achievement is not confined to formal education but extends to a commitment to lifelong learning. Pursuing additional education, attending workshops, and engaging in continuous learning activities are indicative of a proactive approach to staying abreast of developments in a rapidly evolving academic landscape (Bakrie & Syaifuddin, 2023).

Academic achievement is a nuanced and dynamic concept that encompasses a spectrum of accomplishments. From exemplary grades and standardized test scores to active participation in extracurricular activities and the pursuit of advanced degrees, academic achievement reflects an individual's dedication, intellectual curiosity, and commitment to lifelong learning. Beyond the metrics, it is the amalgamation of knowledge, skills, and a passion for learning that defines true academic achievement and shapes individuals into lifelong learners and contributors to society.

Academic achievement is the level of success a child realizes in their academic studies. It is measured by a variety of factors, including grades, test scores, and teacher evaluations. Academic achievement is important for a number of reasons. It can lead to well job prospects, higher income, and a better quality of life. It can also help children grow serious thinking skills, problem-solving skills, and the ability to learn new things (Singh, Sharma & Singh, 2023).

Objectives of the study

1. To identify the parental social support to children at the secondary level.
2. To examine the role of parents' social support in academic achievement of children at secondary level.

Research Methodology

The study was quantitative and descriptive in nature. Survey method was used to collect the data from the respondents. The population of the study consisted of all 1884 students of the 9th and 10th class of Government Boys Secondary Schools in Tehsil Roundu, district Skardu. Simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of a sample from the population. The sample was selected by using Gay (2019) formula. 320 students were selected as a sample of the study. A self developed questionnaire was used for the collection of data for the study. The questionnaire was containing sixteen statements. The response was gathered using a five-point Likert Scale. Each option was assigned numerical value i.e. Strongly Disagree =SDA =1, Disagree=DA2, Undecided=UN=3, Agree =A=4, Strongly Agree=SA=5. The developed questionnaire was validated by two educational experts from the field of Education. For the purposes of pilot testing the questionnaire was distributed among 25 secondary school students who were not part of the final survey. The purpose of pilot testing was to check the useability, readability and reliability of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was measured by Cronbach alpha statistical technique with the help of SPSS software. The reliability of the instrument was found .83 which was acceptable for conducting the final survey. The researcher personally visited the sampled

school and collected the data. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for the analysis of data. The researcher applied frequency, percentage and mean for the analysis of data and interpretation of data. The results presented in the form of tables.

Results

Table 1

My parents help me whenever I need

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	151	121	19	13	16	4.18
Students	320	%	47%	38%	6%	4%	5%

Table 1 indicates that 85% (47% SA+ 38%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents help me whenever I need. Moreover, mean score (M=4.18) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 2

I get the emotional help and support which I need from my parents

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	128	139	22	26	5	4.12
Students	320	%	40%	43%	7%	8%	2%

Table 2 indicates that 83% (40% SA+ 43%A) respondents agreed with the statement that I get the emotional help and support which I need from my parents. Moreover, mean score (M=4.12) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 3

My parents are the source of comfort for me

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	129	142	41	1	7	4.20
Students	320	%	40%	44%	13%	0.3%	2%

Table 3 indicates that 84% (40% SA+ 44%A) respondents agreed with the statement My parents are the source of comfort for me. Moreover, mean score (M=4.20) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 4

I can count on my parents when thing go wrong

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean	
	N	F	119	129	33	30	9	4
Students	320	%	37%	40%	10%	9%	3%	

Table 4 indicates that 77% (37% SA+ 40%A) respondents agreed with the statement that I can count on my parents when thing go wrong. Moreover, mean score (M=4) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 5

I can talk about my problem with my parents

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean	
	N	F	129	125	20	13	33	3.95
Students	320	%	40%	39%	6%	4%	10%	

Table 8 indicates that 79% (40% SA+ 39%A) respondents agreed with the statement that I can talk about my problem with my parents. Moreover, mean score (M=3.95) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 6

I share my all matters with my parents

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean	
	N	F	127	122	12	25	34	3.88
Students	320	%	40%	38%	4%	8%	11%	

Table 6 indicates that 78% (40% SA+ 38%A) respondents agreed with the statement that I share my all matters with my parents. Moreover, mean score (M=3.88) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 7

In my life parents care about my feelings

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	128	128	24	35	5	4.06
Students	320	%	40%	40%	8%	11%	2%

Table 7 indicates that 80% (40% SA+ 40%A) respondents agreed with the statement that In my life parents care about my feelings. Moreover, mean score (M=4.06) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 8

My parents are willing to help me in making my decision

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	129	125	37	23	6	4.09
Students	320	%	40%	39%	12%	7%	2%

Table 8 indicates that 79% (40% SA+ 39%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents are willing to help me in making my decision. Moreover, mean score (M=4.09) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 9

My parents are always there to support me financially

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	133	146	17	7	17	4.16
Students	320	%	42%	46%	5%	2%	5%

Table 9 indicates that 88% (42% SA+ 46%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents are always there to support me financially. Moreover, mean score (M=4.16) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 10

My parents always give me my pocket money

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	141	124	22	11	22	4.10
Students	320	%	44%	39%	7%	3%	7%

Table 10 indicates that 83% (44% SA+ 39%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents always give me my pocket money. Moreover, mean score (M=4.10) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 11

My parents allow me to work as part time

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	112	109	24	48	27	3.72
Students	320	%	35%	34%	8%	15%	8%

Table 11 indicates that 69% (35% SA+ 34%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents allow me to work as part time. Moreover, mean score (M=3.72) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 12

My parents provide me opportunity to visit resorts

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	118	108	40	25	29	3.82
Students	320	%	37%	34%	13%	8%	9%

Table 8 indicates that 71% (37% SA+ 34%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents provide me opportunity to visit resorts. Moreover, mean score (M=3.82) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 13

My parents provide me everything which I need

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	122	136	30	19	13	4.05
Students	320	%	38%	43%	9%	6%	4%

Table 13 indicates that 81% (38% SA+ 43%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents provide me everything which I need. Moreover, mean score (M=4.05) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 14

My parents protect me in the hour of trouble

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	136	127	29	22	6	4.14
Students	320	%	43%	40%	9%	7%	2%

Table 14 indicates that 83% (43% SA+ 40%A) respondents agreed with the statement that my parents protect me in the hour of trouble. Moreover, mean score (M=4.14) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 15

Parents show me how to do things

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	132	143	17	11	17	4.13
Students	320	%	41%	45%	5%	3%	5%

Table 15 indicates that 86% (41% SA+ 45%A) respondents agreed with the statement that Parents show me how to do things. Moreover, mean score (M=4.13) also reflects the opinion of respondents in favor of the statement.

Table 16

My parents show me love

Sample Group		SA	A	UD	DA	SDA	Mean
N	F	146	131	16	15	12	4.20
Students	320	%	46%	41%	5%	5%	4%

Table 16 indicates that 87% (46% SA+ 41%A) respondents agreed with the statement that I am able to end conversations appropriately. Moreover, mean score (M=4.20) also reflects.

Discussion

The results indicate that respondents feel that their parents provide emotional help and support when needed. This aligns with research that emphasizes the significance of emotional support in fostering a child's well-being (Eisenberg et al., 2010). Positive parent-child relationships contribute to children's emotional security and overall mental health.

The results also highlight the willingness of children to talk to their parents about problems and share all matters. Effective parent-child communication is associated with various positive outcomes, including better academic performance and reduced risk of behavioral issues (Ackerman et al., 2013). The findings support the importance of open communication for a healthy parent-child relationship.

The results show that respondents believe their parents support them financially and provide opportunities for personal and academic growth. Research indicates that financial support and access to opportunities positively influence children's educational attainment and career development (Dufur et al., 2015). This emphasizes the role of parents in shaping their children's future by providing resources and encouragement.

The results also imply that parents are perceived as protectors who provide everything their children need and guide them in various aspects of life. Parental guidance is crucial for teaching children essential life skills and helping them navigate challenges (Steinberg, 2001).

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that most of the respondents were agreed that the parents help me whenever I need and I get the emotional help and support which I need from my parents. Moreover, respondents were agreed that the parents are the source of comfort for children they can count on parents when thing go wrong.
2. I t is concluded that most of the respondents were agreed that children can talk with their parents about problems and they share all matters with their parents. Moreover, they agree with that parents are care about children feelings and parents are willing to help them in making decision.
3. It is concluded that most of the respondents were agreed about the relationship of children and parents and give positive response that parents are always there to support their children financially and parents encourage and allow them to work as part time. Moreover, parents provide them opportunity to visit resorts which help them in their achievement.

4. It is concluded that most of respondents were give a positive response about that the parents provide everything which the children need they protect them in the hour of trouble. Moreover, Parents show them how to do things and able them to end conversations appropriately.

Recommendations

The results of the study underscore the importance of fostering strong parent-child relationships by acknowledging and building upon the positive aspects identified. To further enhance family dynamics, it is recommended to promote and celebrate parental responsiveness and emotional support. Encouraging open communication channels between parents and children should be a priority, emphasizing the mutual sharing of concerns and decision-making. Additionally, supporting parents in providing financial assistance and encouraging their children's employment opportunities, as well as facilitating family outings to resorts, can contribute to a well-rounded and enriching upbringing. To sustain the positive environment described, initiatives should focus on promoting parental guidance, creating opportunities for shared activities, and ensuring continuous education for parents to adapt to the evolving needs of their children. Overall, these recommendations aim to strengthen the foundation of positive parent-child relationships and contribute to the overall well-being and development of children within the family unit.

References

- Ackerman, B. P., Brown, E. D., & Izard, C. E. (2004). The relations between contextual risk, earned income, and the school adjustment of children from economically disadvantaged families. *Developmental Psychology*, 40(2), 204–216.
- Adarkwah, M. A. (2021). “I’m not against online teaching, but what about us?”: ICT in Ghana
- Bakrie, T., & Syaifuddin, C. A. P. (2023). Examining the effects of online learning platforms on student satisfaction and academic performance in management study in China. *Central European Management Journal*, 31(3), 369-378.
- Barker, G., Olukoya, A., & Aggleton, P. (2005). Young people, social support and help-seeking. *International journal of adolescent medicine and health*, 17(4), 315-336.
- Cacciatore, J., Thieleman, K., Fretts, R., & Jackson, L. B. (2021). What is good grief support? Exploring the actors and actions in social support after traumatic grief. *PloS one*, 16(5), e0252324.
- Chawla, L. (2020). Childhood nature connection and constructive hope: A review of research on connecting with nature and coping with environmental loss. *People and Nature*, 2(3), 619-642.
- Dufur, M. J., Parcel, T. L., & Troutman, K. P. (2015). Does capital at home matter more than capital at school? Social capital effects on academic achievement. *Research in Social Stratification and Mobility*, 40, 26–37.
- Eisenberg, N., Cumberland, A., Spinrad, T. L., Fabes, R. A., Shepard, S. A., Reiser, M., ... & Guthrie, I. K. (2001). The relations of regulation and emotionality to children's externalizing and internalizing problem behavior. *Child Development*, 72(4), 1112-1134.
- Freak-Poli, R., Ryan, J., Tran, T., Owen, A., McHugh Power, J., Berk, M., ... & Byles, J. (2022). Social isolation, social support and loneliness as independent concepts, and their relationship with health-related quality of life among older women. *Aging & Mental Health*, 26(7), 1335-1344.
- Gariepy, G., Honkaniemi, H., & Quesnel-Vallee, A. (2016). Social support and protection from depression: systematic review of current findings in Western countries. *The British Journal of Psychiatry*, 209(4), 284-293.
- González Yubero, S., Lázaro Visa, S., & Palomera Martín, R. (2021). ¿ Qué aporta la inteligencia emocional al estudio de los factores personales protectores del consumo de alcohol en la adolescencia?
- Gottlieb, B. H., & Bergen, A. E. (2010). Social support concepts and measures. *Journal of psychosomatic research*, 69(5), 511-520.
- Lin, G. X., Goldenberg, A., Arikan, G., Brytek-Matera, A., Czepczor-Bernat, K., Manrique-Millones, D., ... & Gross, J. J. (2022). Reappraisal, social support, and parental burnout. *British Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 61(4), 1089-1102.
- Loveys, K., Sagar, M., Billinghamurst, M., Saffaryazdi, N., & Broadbent, E. (2022, March). Exploring empathy with digital humans. In *2022 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)* (pp. 233-237). IEEE.
- Mahmud, F. H. (2022). ISPAD Clinical Practice Consensus Guidelines 2022: Diabetes education in children and adolescents. *Pediatric Diabetes*, 23(8), 1229.
- Noret, N., Hunter, S. C., & Rasmussen, S. (2020). The role of perceived social support in the relationship between being bullied and mental health difficulties in adolescents. *School Mental Health*, 12, 156-168.
- Olinder, A. L., DeAbreu, M., Greene, S., Haugstvedt, A., Lange, K., Majaliwa, E. S., ... &

- Pasinringi, M. A. A., Vanessa, A. A., & Sandy, G. (2022). The relationship between social support and mental health degrees in emerging adulthood of students. *Golden Ratio of Social Science and Education*, 2(1), 12-23.
- Rodríguez, M. S., Tinajero, C., & Páramo, M. F. (2017). Pre-entry characteristics, perceived social support, adjustment and academic achievement in first-year Spanish university students: A path model. *The Journal of psychology*, 151(8), 722-738.
- Sayfulloevna, S. S. (2023). Safe Learning Environment and Personal Development of Students. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 2(3), 7-12.
- Singh, G., Aiyub, A. S., Greig, T., Naidu, S., Sewak, A., & Sharma, S. (2023). Exploring panic buying behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic: a developing country perspective. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 18(7), 1587-1613.
- Stansfeld, S. A., Marmot, M., & Wilkinson, R. G. (2006). Social determinants of health. de Amorim-Ribeiro, E. M. B., Carneiro, L. L., Martins, L. F., & Cunha, R. C. D. S. (2022). Evaluation Tools of Social Support at Work and Contributions of Social Network Analysis. *Assessing Organizational Behaviors: A Critical Analysis of Measuring Instruments*, 223-241.
- Steinberg, L. (2001). We know some things: Parent–adolescent relationships in retrospect and prospect. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 11(1), 1–19.
- Thangavel, G., Memedi, M., & Hedström, K. (2022). Customized information and communication technology for reducing social isolation and loneliness among older adults: scoping review. *JMIR mental health*, 9(3), e34221.
- Thompson, M. G. (2022). Effectiveness of a third dose of mRNA vaccines against COVID-19–associated emergency department and urgent care encounters and hospitalizations among adults during periods of Delta and Omicron variant predominance—VISION Network, 10 States, August 2021–January 2022. *MMWR. Morbidity and mortality weekly report*, 71.
- Townley, A. (2022). The use of discourse expertise to control the provision of legal services and establish discursive hegemony in commercial law practice: a case study from Europe. *International Journal of Legal Discourse*, 7(1), 1-31.
- Weinraub, M., & Wolf, B. M. (1983). Effects of stress and social supports on mother-child interactions in single-and two-parent families. *Child development*, 1297-1311.
- Zhong, Y., Wang, J., & Nicholas, S. (2020). Social support and depressive symptoms among family caregivers of older people with disabilities in four provinces of urban China: the mediating role of caregiver burden. *BMC geriatrics*, 20(1), 1-10.